

Description of scurvy on the Seventh Crusade by Jean de Joinville (1249)

This is Chapter VII of the book “Saint Louis, King of France” by Jean de Joinville. Joinville’s text is one of the very earliest unambiguous descriptions of scurvy.

Saint Louis, King of France / by the Sire de Joinville; translated by James Hutton. 1892.

<https://archive.org/details/SaintLouisKingOfFrance/page/n13/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/saintlouiskingof0000join/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=njp.32101015301110&seq=13>

Extracts of the section about scurvy:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5294660> (p.207)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5403999> (p.59-60)

<https://www.usni.org/magazines/proceedings/1951/october/million-seamen-were-slain>

This is another translation of the same story on p.432-442:

Chronicles of the crusades, being contemporary narratives of the crusade of Richard Cœur de Lion / by Richard of Devizes and Geoffrey de Vinsauf; and of the crusade of St. Louis, by Lord John de Joinville. 1848. The crusade of Saint Louis translated by T. Johnes.

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/pssvs5ry/items?canvas=446>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=umn.31951p01139215g&seq=444>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044037767399&seq=458>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015000652431&seq=446>

<https://archive.org/details/chroniclesofcrus00join/page/432/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b29349461/page/432/mode/2up>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections.

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

There are earlier texts that had been interpreted as scurvy. However...

James Lind¹ (1757) was not convinced that those older descriptions specifically indicated scurvy.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/296/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=320>

“Not that I would be understood to mean, that the scurvy never afflicted armies of old; but only that the accounts we have of it are dubious and imperfect. The first description of a true scurvy that I have met with, is what occurred in the Christian army in Ægypt, about the year 1260, under *Lewis IX*. But there mention is made, not only of the legs being affected, but also of the spots. The fungous and putrid gums are particularly described, &c.
Vid. Histoire de Lewis IX, par le Sieur Joinville.” p.296.

August Hirsch² (1885) was also not convinced that early writings described scurvy.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179> Section on scurvy separately
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/508/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirs/page/508/mode/2up>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc2.ark:/13960/t39022v3n&seq=526>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015006659547&seq=524>

“The writings that have come down to us from antiquity and the middle ages give no help towards deciding whether scurvy occurred, or was known to medicine, in those times at all; or, if so, to what extent. In order to make out that the Graeco-Roman and Arabian physicians were acquainted with scurvy, special emphasis has been laid on a form of disease described under the name of “*lienes magni*” by Hippocrates, Celsus, Aretæus, Cælius Aurelianus, Paulus Ægineta, Avicenna and others... p.508

There is, in my view, but little reason to take that group of symptoms, characteristic of the “*lienes magni*,” as pointing to scurvy; firstly because swelling of the spleen, which was undoubtedly a constant occurrence in that malady according to the descriptions of observers, is by no means one of the more commonly noted phenomena of scurvy; and secondly because the Hippocratic writers themselves refer the origin of the malady in question to its true source—the malarial cachexia. This view of mine is further supported by the fact, to be afterwards adduced, that scurvy and malarial cachexia have often been confounded in later times... p.509

It is *a priori* highly probable that scurvy had been epidemic from time to time in antiquity under the same circumstances that have given rise to it in the modern p.511

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/James_Lind

2 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/August_Hirsch
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2530992>

period or in recent times. It certainly follows from the account given by Jacques de Vitry^a of a disease called by him the plague, which ravaged the army of the crusaders before Damietta in 1218, and from **Joinville's**^b description

a) Liv. iii, § 351, 'Collect,' Guizot (quoted by Marchand, 'Étude histor. et nosol. sur quelques épidémies et endémies du moyen âge,' Par., 1873, 17):
"Un grande nombre d'hommes de notre armée furent en outre saisis d'une certaine peste contre laquelle les médecins ne pouvaient trouver aucun remède dans leur art. Une douleur soudaine s'emparait des pieds et des jambes: aussitôt après les gencives et les dents étaient attaquées d'une sorte de gangrène, et le malade ne pouvait plus manger. Puis l'os de la jambe devenait horriblement noir et ainsi après avoir souffert de longues douleurs pendant lesquelles ils déployèrent une grande patience, un grand nombre de chrétiens allèrent se reposer dans le sein du Seigneur. Quelques-uns étant parvenus à gagner le printemps se guérirent alors par l'effet des chaleurs."

Translation with Google translate:

"A large number of men in our army were also seized with a certain plague for which doctors could find no remedy in their art. A sudden pain would seize the feet and legs; immediately afterward, the gums and teeth would be attacked by a kind of gangrene, and the patient could no longer eat. Then the leg bone would turn horribly black, and so, after suffering prolonged pain during which they displayed great patience, a large number of Christians went to rest in the bosom of the Lord. Some, having managed to reach spring, were then cured by the effects of the heat."

b) 'Histoire de Saint-Loys,' Par., 1617, 121. "Nousvint une grant persécution et maladie en l'ost ; qui estoit telle que la chair des jambes nous desséchaît jusqu'à l'os, et le cuir nous devenoit tanné de noir et de terre à la ressemblance d'une vieille houze, qui a été longtemp mucée derriere les coffres. En oultre, à nous autres qui auions cette maladie, nous venoit une autre persécution de maladie en la bouche, de ce que nous auions mengié de ces poissons, et nous pourrissoit la chair d'entre les gencives, dont chacun estoit orriblement puant de la bouche. Et à la fin guesres n'en enchappoient que tous ne mourussent. Et le signe de mort que l'on y congnoissoit continuellement estoit quand en se prenoit à saigner du neys, et tantoust on estoit bien assuré d'estre mort de brief."

Translation with Google translate:

A great persecution and illness came upon us in the army; such that the flesh of our legs dried up to the bone, and our leather became tanned black and earthy, like an old hut, which had been moldering for a long time behind the chests. In addition, we who had this illness suffered another persecution of illness in the mouth, from the fact that we had eaten these fish, and our flesh rotted between the gums, making each one stink terribly from the mouth. And in the end, hardly any escaped but all died. And the sign of death that one continually recognized there was when one began to bleed from the nose, and at that moment one was quite sure of having died of heartburn.

of the sickness that broke out in 1250 among the army of Louis IX at the siege of Cairo, that scurvy had existed long before we have any medical recognition or description

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of it as a peculiar form of disease.

The history of scurvy as an epidemic malady well known to the medical profession does not begin before the fifteenth century, or the period of the Renaissance—a movement which touched every relation of life, and by exciting an interest in foreign countries, gave occasion to sea voyages on a scale never before known...”

Hermann Immermann³ (1878) wrote:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17302867> Section on scurvy separately
<https://archive.org/details/63550630RX13.nlm.nih.gov/page/n123/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/b21503230_0017/page/104/mode/2up
<https://collections.nlm.nih.gov/bookviewer?PID.nlm:nlmuid-63550630RX13-mvpart>

In the following brief historical sketch it is not our purpose to present an extended resume of this branch of our subject, but merely to point out those leading facts in the history of the disease which are important for a clear appreciation of its genesis.

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Although neither the medical nor the historical literature of antiquity and the earlier middle ages contains a single passage that discriminates scurvy as a distinct species of disease, or even positively indicates its existence during these periods, it is hardly to be supposed that an affection so closely connected, as scurvy appears to be, with certain widely prevalent sanitary evils—particularly improper diet, hardships, and unfavorable meteorological influences—can have failed to manifest itself in all times whenever individuals or bodies of men have been subjected, under circumstances similar to those of recent times, to the influence of these noxious agents. So far, however, as historical evidence is concerned, the disease can be traced back only as far as the thirteenth century of the present era, and did not acquire actual historical importance as a frequent and widespread affection until about the middle of the fifteenth century, while its present name “scorbutus” made its appearance in medical and non-medical writings only at the beginning of the sixteenth century.

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Attempts have not been wanting to prove the existence of scurvy in ancient times from certain descriptions of disease by the older writers, which have been supposed to refer to the affection in question. None of the evidence, however, will bear careful examination—much of it having no bearing whatever upon the point at issue, while the rest is at least untrustworthy. The most conspicuous instance of this misrepresentation is that which pretends to recognize scurvy in the affection described by Hippocrates, and after him by Aretaeus, Celsus, Caelius Aurelianus, Paulus Aegineta, Avicenna, and others, under the term “(magni lienes)” still, as Hirsch has pointed out, there can be scarcely a doubt that

³ [https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hermann_Immermann_\(Mediziner\)](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hermann_Immermann_(Mediziner))

these “enlarged spleens” are merely what is now known as the lesion of chronic malarial cachexia...

... That the symptoms of this “volvulus sanguineus” strongly resemble those of scurvy cannot be denied; still, neither Hippocrates nor later writers give us any clue to the causes of the affection in question whereby the identity of the latter with scurvy can be satisfactorily established. Such an omission, moreover, when we bear in mind the marked, and indeed, characteristic etiology of scurvy, is fatal to the acceptance of supposed evidence of this kind from the ancient writers; and we can only conclude, therefore, that while the existence of scurvy in early times is *a priori* highly probable, direct proof of the suspected fact is still wanting. On the other hand, we possess unequivocal reports of the occurrence of scurvy at the time of the Crusades, in an epidemic form, and under external conditions completely similar to those ordinarily observed in more recent times, viz., want of food, hardship, unfavorable weather, etc., during marches and sieges. The first epidemic of this kind broke out in November, 1218, at the siege of the city of Damietta, among the forces of Count Saarbrücken,⁴ and continued through the entire winter with great destruction of life. Another epidemic, still more malignant, occurred in 1249, in the army of St. Louis, of France, when it was lying before Cairo and was suddenly deprived of its means of subsistence by an overflow of the Nile. The epidemic of 1218-1219 is described by Jacob de Vitry as follows:

“In vasit praeterea multos de exereitu nova pestis, contra quam physici nullum remedium invenire poterant: dolor repentinus pedes invasit et crura, et conjunctim caro corrupta gingivas et dentes abduxit, masticandi potestatem auferrens; tibias horribilis nigredo offuscavit et sie longo tractu doloris afflicti cum patientia multa migraverunt ad Dominum plurimi; quidam usque ad vernale tempus durantes, beneficio caloris evaserunt liberati.”

Translation with Google translate:

Moreover, many of the army were struck by a new plague, against which physicians could find no remedy: a sudden pain invaded the feet and legs, and at the same time the flesh rotted away the gums and teeth, taking away the power of chewing; the shins were darkened by a horrible blackness, and after a long period of pain, many, with great patience, passed away to the Lord; some, lasting until spring, escaped and were freed by the benefit of the heat.

And **Joinville** relates in regard to the plague of the year 1249:

“Et nous vint la maladie de l’Ost qui étoit telle, que la chair de nos jambes séehoit et étoit tardée de noir et de terre; et à nous qui avions maladie telle venoit chair pourrie aux gengives et nul n’échappoit. Le signe de la mort étoit, que là, ou le nez saignoit, it falloit mourir.”

Translation with Google translate:

And the disease of the Ost came upon us, which was such that the flesh of our legs dried and was tarnished with black and earth; and to us who had such a disease came rotten flesh to the gums, and no one escaped. The sign of death was that where the nose bled, one had to die.

4 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simon_III,_Count_of_Saarbr%C3%BCcken

It is evident from these descriptions, in the thirteenth century, of what we can hardly fail to recognize as scurvy, that the disease had attracted the attention of historians long before it became the object of scientific investigation by physicians.

The immediate occasion of the increased nosological importance which scurvy suddenly acquired for the civilized populations of Europe in the second half of the fifteenth century, and continued to maintain for nearly three hundred years, was the wonderful transformation in the commerce of that epoch initiated by the bold voyages of the Spaniards and Portuguese, beginning with the discovery of America and of the passage to the East Indies... p.110

Alfred Hess⁵ (1920) Scurvy, Past and Present, p.2.

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://catalog.library.cornell.edu/catalog/2903792>

<https://reader.library.cornell.edu/docviewer/digital?id=chla2903792#page/9/mode/1up>

<https://archive.org/details/cu31924073869996/page/n17/mode/2up>

An interesting early description of scurvy, and one which is quite convincing, is that of **de Joinville**, who accompanied the Crusaders in their invasion of Egypt under St. Lewis, about the middle of the thirteenth century. He refers to the lividity and spongy condition of the gums, and describes how “the barber surgeons were forced to cut away the dead flesh from the gums to enable the people to masticate their food”; he describes their debility, their tendency to faint, and the black spots on their legs. The disease broke out in Lent, during which time the soldiers partook of no meat, but consumed a species of eel which they believed “ate the dead people” and therefore led to this loathsome disease.

5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alfred_Fabian_Hess

General background for the Seventh Crusade:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Seventh_Crusade

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Mansurah_\(1250\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Mansurah_(1250))

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Fariskur_\(1250\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Fariskur_(1250))

https://www.worldhistory.org/Seventh_Crusade/

<https://historylearning.com/medieval-england/the-crusades/seventh-crusade/>

<https://the-orb.arlima.net/textbooks/crusade/seventhcr.html>

<https://deremilitari.org/2014/01/the-seventh-crusade-1249-according-to-abu-al-faraj-gregory-bar-hebraeus/>

Scurvy in Louis IX

The above authors point out that there are no unambiguous historical descriptions of scurvy before the crusades; however, with the improvements in research technology, there are archaeological evidence of scurvy in earlier skeletons.⁶

Recent investigations of the skeletal remains suggested that Louis IX may have suffered from scurvy⁷, though the interpretations have been challenged.⁸ In any case, the epidemic of scurvy described in Chapter VII of Joinville's text is such short that it is a highly unlikely explanation for permanent changes in bone structure.

6 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37337361>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30298514>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29539463>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16323179>

7 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37884212>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31185300>
<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/fear-foreign-food-led-death-crusader-king-180972491>
<https://phys.org/news/2019-06-locals-scurvy-undid-crusader-king.html>
<https://www.archaeology.wiki/blog/2019/06/26/french-king-louis-ix-had-severe-scurvy-study-finds>
<https://archaeology.org/news/2019/06/24/190624-king-louis-scurvy>

8 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31904527>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31904525>

Chapter VII.

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<https://archive.org/details/saintlouiskingof0000join/page/n81/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/SaintLouisKingOfFrance/page/n97/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=njp.32101015301110&seq=97>

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AFTER the two battles above described the army began to experience great misery; for at the end of nine days the dead bodies of our people who had fallen rose to the surface of the water (and it was said that this happened because their gall-bladders had putrefied), and they floated to the bridge that joined the two camps, and could not pass through because the bridge rested upon the water. There was such a number of them that the whole surface of the river was covered with dead bodies from one bank to the other, and for the distance of a stone's-throw up the stream. The king engaged a hundred of the camp-followers, who were occupied for eight days. The dead bodies of the Saracens,¹¹ who were circumcised, they threw over to the other side of the bridge, and let them float down the current; but the Christians they buried in deep trenches, one with another. I saw there the Count of Artois' ¹² chamberlains and many others looking for their friends among the dead, but I never heard that any one was identified.

We had no fish in the camp to eat during Lent¹³ except the *karmout* (a kind of eel), which preyed upon the dead bodies, for they are a gluttonous fish. And in con-

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sequence of this misfortune, and of the unhealthiness of the country, where never a drop of rain falls, **we were**

attacked with the army sickness, which was such that our legs shrivelled up and became covered with black spots, and spots of the colour of earth, like an old boot; and in such of us as fell sick the gums became putrid with sores, and no man recovered of that sickness, but all had to die. It was a sure sign of death when the nose began to bleed: there was nothing left then but to die. About a fortnight afterwards **the Turks, in order to starve us out** (at which many of our people were astonished), took several of their galleys which were above our camp, dragged them overland to a good league below our camp, and placed them in the river by which supplies came from Damietta.¹⁴ **These galleys brought famine upon us, for no one now ventured to come to us from Damietta to bring us provisions by ascending the stream.** We knew nothing of all this until a small vessel of the count of Flanders, which fought its way past them, brought us the news, by which time the sultan's galleys had captured eighty of our galleys that were coming from Damietta, and killed all who were on board.

There thence arose such a scarcity in the camp that when Easter had arrived an ox was worth 80 livres,¹⁵ a sheep 30 livres, a pig 30 livres, an egg 12 deniers,¹⁶ and a 60-gallon measure of wine 10 livres.

When the king and the barons saw that, they agreed that the king should withdraw his army from before

9 Saint Louis

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Louis_IX_of_France

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Louis-IX>

<https://www.sainte-chapelle.fr/en/discover/saint-louis>

<https://www.inquiriesjournal.com/articles/96/jean-de-joinville-and-his-biography-of-saint-louis-on-the-seventh-crusade>

<https://catholicinsight.com/2025/08/25/saint-louis-ix-a-most-christian-king/>

<https://www.vaticanstate.va/en/state-and-government/general-informations/saint-of-the-day/2635-august-25-saint-louis-ix-king-of-france.html>

10 Jean de Joinville

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jean_de_Joinville

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Jean-sire-de-Joinville>

11 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saracen>

12 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robert_I,_Count_of_Artois

13 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lent> Period of preparation for Easter.

14 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Damietta>

15 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/French_livre

16 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/French_denier

Babylon,¹⁷ and join the camp of the Duke of Burgundy,¹⁸ which was on the river that goes to Damietta. To effect a junction of his troops with greater safety, the king threw up an outwork¹⁹ before the bridge between the two camps, so that it could be entered on horseback

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from two sides. As soon as the outwork was completed the king's army was put in array, and the Turks made a fierce assault upon the camp. For all that, neither the camp nor any of the people moved until all the baggage had been carried across then: the king crossed, and with him his division, and after that all the other barons, excepting Monseigneur de Châtillon, who covered the retreat. And at the very moment of entering the outwork, Monseigneur Erard de Valery²⁰ rescued Monseigneur John, his brother, whom the Turks were carrying off a prisoner.

When the main body of the army had crossed over, those who remained in the outwork were in great danger; for the outwork was not high, so that the Turks on horseback fired at them point-blank, while the Saracens on foot flung clods²¹ of earth into their faces. They would all have been cut off had not the Count of Anjou,²² who was afterwards King of Sicily, gone to their rescue and brought them off safe and sound. The honour of that day fell to Monseigneur Geoffrey de Mussamboure, from out of all who were in the outwork.

On the eve of Shrove-Tuesday²³ I witnessed a wonderful thing, which I should like to recount to you, for on that day was interred²⁴ Monseigneur Hugh de Landricourt, who was in my company bearing a banner. While he was lying on his bier²⁵ in my chapel, six of my knights were leaning against some sacks of barley: and because they were talking aloud in my chapel and disturbing the priest with their noise, I went up to them and told them to be silent, and said that it was unbecoming in knights and gentlemen to talk while mass was being chanted. But they only laughed, and an-

swered jestingly that they would find another husband for his widow. Then I rebuked them, and said that such

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words were neither wise nor witty, and that they had very soon forgotten their comrade. And God took such vengeance for this, that on the morrow, at the great battle of Shrove-Tuesday, they were all killed or mortally wounded; and it happened that all their six wives married a second time.²⁶

In consequence of the wounds I had received on Shrove-Tuesday, the army sickness attacked me in the mouth and legs, besides a double tertian fever and so severe a cold in the head that the mucus ran from my nostrils,²⁷ and on account of these sicknesses, I took to my bed until mid-Lent. My priest therefore chanted the mass in my tent in front of my bed, and he, too, had the same illness. Whence it came to pass that while in the aet²⁸ of consecrating the elements, he turned faint. Seeing that he was like to fall, I, who had put on my tunic, sprang out of bed barefooted, and held him in my arms, and told him to complete the consecration leisurely and properly, for that I would not let go of him until he had finished. He soon recovered himself, completed the consecration, and finished chanting the mass to the end; but he never chanted it again.

After these things the counsellors of the king and of the sultan appointed a day for a conference. The following conditions were agreed to:—That Damietta should be restored to the sultan, who should give up to the king the kingdom of Jerusalem; and the sultan was to take charge of the sick who were at Damietta, and the salted meat (for they never touch pork), and the king's engines, until such time as he should send for them all. Then they asked the king's counsellors what security they would give that Damietta should be restored. The king's counsellors proposed that they should detain one of the king's brothers, either the

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17 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babylon_Fortress

18 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hugh_IV,_Duke_of_Burgundy

19 Outwork. A minor fortification built or established outside the principal fortification limits, detached or semidetached. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outwork>

20 https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:%C3%89rard_of_Val%C3%A9ry
https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/%C3%89rard_de_Vallery

21 Clod. A lump of earth or clay.

22 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Charles_I_of_Anjou

23 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shrove_Tuesday The traditional feast day before the start of Lent.

24 Inter. To deposit (a dead body) in the earth or in a tomb.

25 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bier> A bier is a stand on which a corpse, coffin, or casket containing a corpse is placed.

26 <https://nobility.org/2014/04/six-knights-are-punished-for-disrespect-at-mass/>

27 In this context, "mouth and legs" indicate scurvy, whereas fever and mucus may indicate e.g. virus infection.

28 Aet. Age.

Count of Anjou or the Count of Poitiers,²⁹ until the restoration of Damietta. The Saracens replied that they would make no treaty unless the king's own person was left with them in pledge; whereupon Monseigneur Geoffrey de Sargines,³⁰ the good knight, declared that he would rather that the Saracens should take or kill them to a man, than that he should ever hear himself reproached with having left the king in pledge.

The sickness became much more severe throughout the camp, and the proud flesh³¹ in our men's mouths grew to such excess that the barber-surgeons were obliged to cut it off, to give them a chance of chewing their food or swallowing anything. It was piteous to hear through the camp the shrieks of the people who were being operated upon for proud flesh, for they shrieked like women in childbirth.

When the king perceived that he could remain there no longer without himself and his people all perishing, he gave orders and instructions for setting out on Tuesday evening, at nightfall, after the octave of Easter, with the intention of returning to Damietta. The king commanded Jocelyn de Cornaut, his brothers, and the other engineers, to sever the ropes which fastened the bridges between us and the Saracens; but they did not. We embarked on the Tuesday in the afternoon, after dinner, I and the two knights who remained to me of all my company. When the hour of nightfall arrived I bade the mariners raise the anchor and let us float down with the stream; but they said they dared not, because the sultan's galleys which were between us and Damietta would put us to death. The mariners had kindled large fires to gather the sick to their galleys, and the latter had drawn down to the bank of the river. While I was entreating the ship's people to start, the

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Saracens broke into the camp, and I saw by the light of the fires that they were slaughtering the sick by the river-side. While my mariners were raising the anchor, those whose duty it was to bring off the sick cut the ropes of their anchors and galleys, and came down upon our small vessels, pressing us so close together that they narrowly missed sending us to the bottom. When we had got clear of this danger, and were dropping down the river, the king, who was suffering much from the army sickness and from dysentery, could have

saved himself on board the galleys had he pleased, but he answered that, please God, he would not quit his people. In the evening he fainted several times. They cried out to us who were on the river to wait for the king, and when we refused to wait they fired upon us with bolts, wherefore we were obliged to wait until they should give us permission to set sail.

I will now tell you how the king was made prisoner, as he himself related it to me. He said that he had left his own division, and, together with Monseigneur Geoffrey de Sargines, had joined the corps of Monseigneur Walter de Châtillon, which formed the rear-guard. And the king said that he was mounted on a little hack,³² with a housing of silk, and that behind him of all his knights and sergeants there remained only Monseigneur Geoffrey de Sargines, who conducted the king to the village in which he was taken; and the king told me that Monseigneur Geoffrey de Sargines defended him against the Saracens just as a good valet drives away the flics from his master's cup; for each time the Saracens drew near he clapped his spear—which he carried between himself and the saddle-bow—under his arm, and charged them and drove them away from the king. And in this manner he brought him on to the village, and they car-

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ried the king into a house, and laid him all but dead in the lap of a woman of the burgher class³³ from Paris, and they thought he would not hold out till the evening. Thither came Monseigneur Philip de Montfort,³⁴ and said to the king that he saw the emir with whom he had negotiated for a truce, and that, if he pleased, he would go to him and conclude the truce upon the terms demanded by the Saracens. The king prayed him to go, for that he much wished it. He went to the Saracen, who took off his turban from his head and the ring from his finger, as a pledge that he would keep faith. In the meanwhile a great misfortune befell our people, for a traitor sergeant, named Marcel, began to call out to them: "Sir knights, yield yourselves, for such is the king's pleasure, and do not cause the king to be put to death." All believed that such was the king's command, and surrendered their swords to the Saracens. The emir observed that the Saracens were leading our people away captive. Then he said to Monseigneur Philip that it was not fitting that he should accord a

29 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alphonse,_Count_of_Poitiers

30 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Geoffrey_of_Sergines

31 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Granulation_tissue Proud flesh. An excessive growth of granulation tissue.

32 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hack_\(horse\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hack_(horse))

33 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Burgher_\(social_class\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Burgher_(social_class))

34 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philip_of_Montfort,_Lord_of_Tyre

truce to our people, for he saw that they were prisoners. Thus it happened to Monseigneur Philip that all our people were prisoners excepting himself, because he was an envoy. Now, there is a bad custom in the country of the Paynim,³⁵ which is, that when the king sends messengers to the sultan, or the sultan to the king, and either the king or the sultan dies before the messengers return, those messengers become prisoners or slaves to whichever side they belong, whether Christians or Saracens.

While this misfortune overtook our people who were on land, the same thing happened to us who were on the water; for the wind blew from Damietta, and counteracted the current, and the knights whom the king had placed in his light vessels to defend the sick fled

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away. Our sailors, too, left the main stream and got into a creek, so that we were obliged to turn back again towards the Saracens.

As we were going along by water, we came, just before the dawn broke, to the passage where were lying the sultan's galleys that had prevented supplies from coming to us from Damietta. A great tumult arose, for they fired against ourselves and against our people who were riding along the bank of the river such a quantity of darts dipped in Greek fire³⁶ that it seemed as if the stars were falling from the skies.

When our sailors had extricated us from the arm of the river into which we had strayed, we came upon the king's light boats which the king had assigned for the protection of our sick fleeing in all haste to Damietta. Then a wind arose coming from Damietta, which blew so strong as to neutralize the current. On both sides of the river there was a great number of small boats belonging to our people which were unable to make downward way, and had been stopped and captured by the Saracens. And they put the people to death and threw their bodies into the water, and pulled out the chests and baggage from the vessels they had taken. The Saracens who were upon the bank on horseback kept on discharging darts at us because we would not go to them. My people had fastened upon me a tourney hauberk,³⁷ which I had put on lest some of the darts which fell into our vessel might wound me. At that moment my people who were in the forepart of the ves-

sel called out to me: "Sir, sir, your sailors, because the Saracens are threatening them, mean to take you ashore." I raised myself up by my arms, weak as I was, and drew my sword upon them, and declared that I would slay them if they took me ashore. They replied

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that I might choose which I would have done, either they would take me ashore, or they would anchor in the middle of the river until the wind went down. I told them that I would rather they anchored in the middle of the river than be taken ashore, where I saw we should be slain, so they let go the anchor.

It was not long before we saw four of the sultan's galleys approach, with a thousand men on board. Then I called my knights and my people, and asked what they desired we should do, whether surrender ourselves to the Sultan's galleys, or to the people who were on the bank.

We all agreed that we should prefer surrendering ourselves to the sultan's galleys, because they would keep us all together, to surrendering ourselves to those who were on the land, because they would separate us, and sell us to the Bedaween.³⁸ Then one of my clerks, who was a native of Doullens, said: "Sir, I do not hold to this council." I asked him to what he would hold, and he said: "I am of opinion that we should let ourselves be killed, so shall we all go to Paradise." But we did not agree with him.

When I saw that we must be taken, I threw a casket, with my jewels and relies, into the river. Then one of my sailors said to me: "Sir, **if you do not let me say that you are the king's cousin, they will put us all to death, and you with us.**" I told him that I was quite willing that he should say what he pleased. When the people in the first galley, who were coming to run us down amidships, heard that, they cast out their anchors close to our vessel. Then God sent a Saracen, who was of the emperor's land, who swam to our vessel, and, throwing his arms round me, said: "Sir, you are lost if you do not act with resolution, for you must leap

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from your vessel on to the beak of that galley: if you take the leap they will not notice you, for they are thinking of the plunder of your vessel." They threw

35 Paynim. Muslim, paganism.

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/paynim>

36 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Greek_fire

37 Hauberk. A tunic of chain mail worn as defensive armor from the 12th to the 14th century.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hauberk>

<https://www.clevelandart.org/art/1923.1120>

38 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bedouin>

me a rope from the galley, and I sprang on to the beak, as it pleased God. But I tottered, and had not the Saracen leaped after me, to support me, I should have fallen into the water.

They took me into the galley, where there were at least 280 of their men, and he kept his arm always round me. Then the others threw me down, and jumped upon my body to cut my throat, for whoever killed me would have felt himself honoured. But this Saracen always held me in his arms, and kept calling out, "The king's cousin !" Twice they threw me down, and once upon my knees, and then I felt the knife at my throat. In this ordeal God preserved me by means of this Saracen, who brought me to the tower (on the deck) in which the Saracen knights were assembled. When I came into the midst of them, they took off my hauberk, and, moved by compassion, threw over me a scarlet coverlid, lined with miniver³⁹ which my lady mother had given me, and one of them brought me a white girdle, with which I girt myself outside my coverlid, in which I had made a hole and had put it on; and another brought me a hood which I put over my head. And then, because of the fear I had, and also because of my illness, I began greatly to tremble. And I asked for something to drink, and they brought me some in a vessel; but as soon as I took it in my mouth to swallow it, it spurted out of my nostrils. When I saw that, I sent for my people, and told them I was a dead man, for I had a gathering in my throat. They asked me how I knew that, and as soon as they saw the water come out of my throat and nostrils, they began to weep.

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When the Saracen knights who were there saw my people weeping, they asked the Saracen who had saved our lives why they were weeping. And he replied that he thought I had a gathering in the throat, and therefore it was all over with me. Then one of the Saracen knights told him who had saved us to bid us be of good cheer, for he would give me something to take that would cure me in two days, and he did so.

The grand-admiral of the galleys sent for me, and asked me if I was the king's cousin. And I answered him no; and told him how and why the sailor had said that I was. He replied that I had acted wisely, for otherwise we should all have been dead men. Then he asked me if I was in any way connected with the

Emperor Frederick⁴⁰ of Germany, who was at that time living. And I answered that I believed my mother was his cousin-german. Upon which he said that he should like me all the better for it. While we were at dinner, he sent for a burgess⁴¹ of Paris; and when the burgess came he said to me: "Sir, what are you doing ?"

"What am I doing then ?" I asked.

"Why, in God's name," exclaimed he, "you are eating meat on Friday !"

When I heard that, I put my trencher⁴² behind me. Then the admiral asked my Saracen why I did that, and he told him. And the admiral observed that God would not be angered with me for what I had done, as I did not do it wittingly. And that is the very answer the legate made me when we were out of captivity. But for all that I have not since omitted to fast on bread and water every Friday in Lent, on which account the legate was very angry with me, because there remained near the king no other rich man than myself. The Sunday afterwards the admiral ordered myself, and all

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the other prisoners who had been taken upon the water, to be landed on the bank. While they were dragging Monseigneur John, my good priest, out of the hold of the galley, he fainted, whereupon they killed him, and threw him into the river. His clerk, who also fainted through the army sickness which was upon him, had a cap clapped upon his head; but he, too, was slain, and flung into the river. While the other invalids were being landed from the galleys in which they had been imprisoned, there were Saracens ready with drawn swords to put to death all who fell, and who were then cast into the river. I said to them, by means of my Saracen, that it seemed to me that they were acting wrongly, because it was contrary to Saladin's⁴³ instructions, who declared that no one ought to take a man's life after allowing him to partake of his bread and salt. The admiral replied that they were men of no account, for they were unable to hold up against the sickness that was upon them. He ordered my sailors to be brought before me, and said that they had all abjured Christianity. I told him not to place any trust in them, for they would abandon him just as readily as they had abandoned us. The admiral made answer that he agreed with me, for Saladin had said that he never knew a good Saracen become a good Christian, or a good Christian become a

39 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Miniver>

40 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Frederick_II,_Holy_Roman_Emperor

41 <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/burgess>

42 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trencher_\(tableware\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trencher_(tableware))

43 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saladin> A Kurdish political leader; the first sultan of both Egypt and Syria (1137–1193).

good Saracen. After these things, he mounted me upon a palfrey, and made me go by his side. And we crossed a bridge of boats, and went to Mansourah,⁴⁴ where the king and his army were prisoners. And we came to the entrance of a large tent, in which were the sultan's scribes, and they made me write my name. Then my Saracen said to me: "Sir, I cannot follow you any further, but I pray you, sir, to hold always by the hand the child you have with you, lest the Saracens should

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carry him off from you." And this child was named Bartholomew, and was the bastard of the Seigneur de Montfaucon. As soon as my name was written down, the admiral led me to the tent where the barons were and upwards of 10,000 people with them. When I entered, all the barons expressed so much joy, that not a word could be heard; and they gave thanks to our Lord, and said they thought I was lost.

⁴⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mansoura,_Egypt
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Mansurah_\(1250\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Battle_of_Mansurah_(1250))